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Research Article

Role Of Clinical Pharmacist In Patient Counselling And Improving Medication Adherence In Patients With Respiratory Disorders In A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital - A Prospective Interventional Study

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ABSTRACT

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Background: Medication adherence is the extent to which a person's behaviour coincides with health-related advice and take medications as prescribed, make possible life style changes.

Objectives: To evaluate the role of clinical pharmacist in the management of respiratory diseases including improvement in medication adherence, quality of life and to Identify risk factors.

Methodology: A Prospective interventional analytical study was conducted on a sample size of 250 patients and only 226 patient's data was collected and counselled based on inclusion criteria and remaining 24 patient's data was missing.

Results: A total 226 patients of different respiratory diseases were included in the study. Out of 226 patients, In age group-73 patients of 65-75 years are with 32.2%. In gender: 139 (61.5%) patients were male and 97 (42.9%) patients were female. In financial status: 148 (65.4%) patients were under below poverty line and 80 (35.3%) patients were under above poverty line. In type of disease: 74 (32.74%) patients were diagnosed with COPD, 58 (25.6%) patients were diagnosed with Asthma, 40 (17.6%) patients were diagnosed with Tuberculosis, 52 (23%) patients were diagnosed with Other Respiratory diseases.

Conclusion: The study concludes that patient counselling have significant influence in improving patient's medication adherence. Chi-square test was done. X^2 value for patients with improved medication adherence is 205.8 with degrees of freedom 1, p value is 0.0001 so $p < 0.05$, hence there is a statistically significance.

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INTRODUCTION:

Respiratory disease is a medical term that encompasses pathological conditions affecting the organs and tissues that make gas exchange difficult in higher organisms and includes conditions of the upper respiratory tract, trachea, bronchi, bronchioles, alveoli, pleura, pleural cavity, and the nerves and muscles of breathing. Respiratory diseases range from mild and self-limiting, such as the common cold, to life-threatening entities like bacterial pneumonia, pulmonary embolism, acute asthma and lung cancer. The study of respiratory disease is known as pulmonology. Respiratory diseases remain a major public health problem in worldwide, with increasing morbidity and mortality⁽¹⁾. Respiratory diseases can be classified in many different ways, including by the organ or tissue involved, the type and pattern of associated signs and symptoms, or the cause of the disease⁽²⁾. Asthma is a common long-term inflammatory disease of the airways of the lungs. It is characterized by variable and recurring symptoms of reversible airflow obstruction and bronchospasm. Symptoms include episodes of wheezing, coughing, chest tightness, and shortness of breath⁽³⁾.

Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease as “a preventable and treatable disease. Characterized by airflow limitation that is not fully reversible. The airflow limitation is usually progressive and associated with an abnormal inflammatory response of the lung to noxious particles or gases⁽⁴⁾. loss of lung function is caused by emphysema due to destruction of lung parenchyma and by narrowing of small airways as a result of chronic inflammation and fibrosis and loss of elastic recoil. This results in progressive airflow limitation, air trapping, and progressive shortness of breath on exertion⁽⁵⁾

A variety of viruses and bacteria can cause upper respiratory tract infections. Upper respiratory tract infections involve the nose, sinuses, pharynx, larynx, and the large airways. These cause a variety of patient diseases including acute bronchitis, the common cold, influenza, and respiratory distress syndromes. ⁽⁶⁾

Acute lower respiratory tract infections are a persistent and pervasive public health problem. The outcome of an acute lower respiratory tract infection

depends on the virulence of the organism (bacterial or viral pneumonia) and the inflammatory response in the lung. Acute inflammation features the accumulation of neutrophils and a plasma exudate outside of blood vessels.⁽⁷⁾ Tuberculosis (TB) is an airborne infectious disease caused by organisms of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. Although primarily a pulmonary pathogen, *M. tuberculosis* can cause disease in almost any part of the body. Infection with *M. tuberculosis* can evolve from containment in the host, in which the bacteria are isolated within granulomas (latent TB infection), to a contagious state, in which the patient will show symptoms that can include cough, fever, night sweats and weight loss. Only active pulmonary TB is contagious.⁽⁸⁾

A clinical pharmacist plays an important role in overcoming the barriers to improve medication adherence through effective patient counselling. Adherence to medication regimen is generally defined as the extent to which patient take medications prescribed by their health care provider. Adherence to therapy is a challenge not only for the patient but also health practitioner and researcher. ⁽⁹⁾

A study of medication adherence in patients with respiratory disorders is important to assess the effectiveness of the therapy for obtaining symptomatic control. One of the methods to measure adherence to medication is the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS) questionnaire that consists of 8 questions. ⁽¹⁰⁾

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research type was a prospective Observational and Pharmacist Interventional study. The study was carried out for a period of 8 months at MNR Hospital (A tertiary care teaching hospital) located at Sangareddy, Telangana state.

Obtaining clearance certificate from institutional ethics committee (iec)

For obtaining ethical clearance certificate, an application along with study protocol which includes the proposed title, study site, inclusion and exclusion criteria, objectives and methodology about the work to be carried out was submitted to the chairman of IEC. The study was conducted after obtaining the ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee.

Privacy and Confidentiality were ensured during the clinical care services.

Data Collection

The sample size of the present study was 226 patients with respiratory disorders after thorough screening of inclusion and exclusion criteria. A separate data collection form and a MMAS questionnaire form were designed to take the patient's demographic details, family history, medical history, diagnosis, medication history, factors affecting medication adherence and reasons for medication non-adherence.

ASSESSMENT OF MEDICATION ADHERENCE:

The medication adherence was assessed by using Morisky Medication Adherence Assessment questionnaires.

Baseline assessment:

The baseline adherence of the patients was assessed at their first visit. This session was performed during patient's interview followed by standardized counselling session that allowed determining the use of inhaler, patient understanding of his medication, his behaviour towards the treatment, and the reasons for medication non-adherence.

Follow up:

First follow up was conducted after 1 week of patient's discharge and medication adherence was assessed and score was given. Similarly, II and III follow ups were conducted.

Data collection and scoring:

Data was collected either directly from patient or from their case sheets by using case report forms. The medication adherence assessment score was given on the basis of number of questions answered correctly i.e. if the patient answered 'NO' it carries 1 score and 'YES' it carries 0 score for the question. The Morisky medication adherence score was collected for every follow up and analysed for the improvement of medication adherence.

Outcome variables:

The primary outcome was significant improvement in the patient medication adherence. The risk factors which are responsible for the prevalence of respiratory diseases and the reasons for the medication non-adherence were also analysed.

Statistical analysis

Data obtained were entered and analysed using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 22 to obtain p value. A p value of <0.005 was obtained and considered to be statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Out of 226 patients, 25 patients are found in the age group between 25-35 years of age with 12.5% followed by 30 patients in the age group between 36-45 years with 14.7%, 39 patients were found in the age group between 46-55 with 13.9%, 62 patients were found in the age group between 56-65 with 25%, followed by 73 patients in the age group between 66-75 with 33.8%. The age group which is of higher risk is 65-75 years as the older people immune system undergoes gradual weakening with age. The results are tabulated in table No:1 and well-illustrated in the figure No:1

Out of 226 patients diagnosed with pulmonary disorders, 139 patients with 61.5% were found to be male and 87 patients with 38.4% were found to be female. Male patients are at higher risk compared with female patients. The results are tabulated in table No:2 and the same is depicted in the figure No:2

Out of 226 patients, 146 patients with 64.6% were taken under below poverty line and 80 patients with 35.3% were taken under above poverty line. The results are tabulated in table No:3 and the same is depicted in the figure No:3

Out of 226 patients, the major risk factor for respiratory disorders was found to be smoking and alcohol with 34.55% followed by smoking with 20.3%, alcohol and tobacco in any form with 19%, tobacco in any form with 12.3%, alcohol with 9.7% and hereditary with 3.9%. The results are tabulated in table No: 4 and well-illustrated in the figure No: 4

Out of 226 patients 74 patients with 32.7% were diagnosed with COPD, 58 patients with 25.6% were diagnosed with Asthma, 42 patients with 18.5% were diagnosed with Tuberculosis, 52 patients with 23% were diagnosed with other diseases. The results are tabulated in table No: 5 and the same is depicted in the figure No: 5

Out of 226 patients, 158 patients with 69% are provided with antibiotics, 160 patients with 70% are provided with glucocorticoids, 142 patients

with 62% are provided with NSAIDs, and 153 patients with 67% are provided with salbutamol. The results are tabulated in table No: 6 and well-illustrated in the figure No: 6.

Out of 226 patients, 43 patients with 19% are due to polypharmacy and 37 patients with 16.3% are due to lack of knowledge and 22 patients with 9.6% are due to lack of immediate effect, 33 patients with 14.6% are due to fear of side effects, 28 patients with 12.3% are due to high cost, 21 patients with 9.2% are due to treatment considered ineffective, 15 patients with 6.6% are due to depression, 11 patients with 4.8% are due to poor inhalation techniques, 9 patients with 3.9% are due to forgetfulness, 7 patients with 3% are due to other reasons. The results are tabulated in table No: 7 and the same is depicted in the figure No: 7

Out of 226 patients, 17 patients are found to show high medication adherence, 72 patients

showed medium and 137 patients showed low medication adherence at base line. During first follow-up 75 patients have shown high improvement in their medication adherence, 54 patients with medium improvement, 97 patients with low improvement. During second follow-up, 136 patients have shown high improvement in their medication adherence, 43 have shown medium improvement, 47 patients have shown low improvement. During third follow-up 168 patients are shown high improvement, 35 have shown medium and 23 have shown low improvement in medication adherence. Chi-square test has been performed. X^2 value for patients with improved medication adherence is 205.8 with degrees of freedom 1, p value is 0.0001 so $p < 0.05$ hence there is a statistically significant difference between before and after counselling. The results are tabulated in table No: 8 and well-illustrated in the figure No: 8.

Table 1: Age Distribution of the sample

Age(years)	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
25-35	25	12.5%
36-45	30	14.7%
46-55	39	13.9%
56-65	62	25%
66-75	73	33.8%

Figure 1: Age Distribution of the sample

Table 2: Gender Distribution of the sample

Gender	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Male	139	61.5%
Female	87	38.4%

Figure 2: Gender Distribution of the sample

Table 3: Financial status

Financial status	No. of cases	Percentage(%)
Below Poverty line	146	64.6%
Above Poverty line	80	35.3%

Figure 3: Financial status

Table no 4: Risk factors

Risk Factors	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Smoking	36	15.9%
Alcohol	22	9.7%
Tobacco in any other form	18	7.9%
Hereditary	9	3.9%
Smoking and Alcohol	68	30%
Alcohol and Tobacco in any form	36	15.9%
None	37	16.7%

Figure 4: Risk factors

Table 5: Type of disease

Type of disease	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
COPD	74	32.7%
Asthma	58	25.6%
Tuberculosis	42	18.5%
Other	52	23%

Figure 5: Type of disease

Table 6: Drug Therapy

Drugs	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Antibiotics	158	69%
Glucocorticoids	160	70%
NSAIDs	142	62%
Salbutamol	153	67%

Figure 6: Drug Therapy

Table 7: Reason for non-medication adherence vs number of cases

Reasons	No. of cases	Percentage (%)
Polypharmacy	43	19%
Lack of knowledge	37	16.3%
Lack of immediate effect	22	9.6%
Fear of side effects	33	14.6%
High cost	28	12.3%
Treatment considered ineffective	21	9.2%
Depression	15	6.6%
Poor inhalation technique	11	4.8%
Forgetfulness/Occupation related problems	9	3.9%
Others	7	3%

Figure 7: Reason for non-medication adherence vs number of cases

Table 8: Score of Morisky medication

Medication adherence score	Baseline	Follow up 1	Follow up 2	Follow up 3	Level of significance
High adherence (1-2)	17	75	136	168	P(0.0001)
Medium adherence (3-5)	72	54	43	35	
Low adherence (6-8)	137	97	47	23	

Figure 8: Score of Morisky medication

CONCLUSION

Age group of 65-75 years patients were more prone to respiratory disorder which may be due to decreased immune response as the age increased which is followed by age group of 55-65 and a smaller number of disorder where seen in the age group of 25-35.

Males were more prone to respiratory disorders when compared to females because of their occupational and lifestyle related factors which may cause more complications which leads to the prevalence of disorders.

Glucocorticoids were more commonly prescribed when compared to other medications and patients need to be monitored for the altered glucose levels as the glucocorticoids may cause alteration of glucose levels, followed by antibiotics.

Polypharmacy was focused to be the primary reason for non-medication adherence. Personal care and attention should be taken as most of the diagnosed patients were between 65-75 years of age which they may suffer with age related amnesia. We took care of patient's polypharmacy problems by counselling and educating the patients to overcome the polypharmacy problems by using simple technique like calendar technique.

More irrationality was observed among patients who were prescribed with antibiotics because of their age-related factors or lack of symptoms or polypharmacy related factors. We have counselled the patients regarding the importance of rational use of medication to get complete cure from ailments. Physicians should consider the pharmacist suggestion which will ultimately give benefit to the patient.

Clinical pharmacist by using his patient counselling techniques and skills could improve the medication adherence of the patient by monitoring and educating the patients which will ultimately give the benefit to the patients and improve overall quality of life.

Further research is to be done by considering the large sample size, so that the accuracy can be achieved.

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